

A single - device universal logic gate based on a magnetically enhanced memristor

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Since its experimental realization, the Memristor became one of the most promising candidates for the post-CMOS era. The concept of the memristor was introduced theoretically in 1971 by Leon Chua^[1] as the fourth basic circuit element alongside resistance, capacitance and inductance. The defining property of the memristor is the non-volatile variation of its resistance, called memristance, which is dependent on the history of the applied current or voltage. Even if similar non-volatile resistance switching effects were already known in the 60's^[2, 3], a complete realisation of a memristor device, together with its phenomenological model had to wait more than fifty years, until the recently published pioneering paper by Strukov et al.^[4, 5]. Since then memristor devices and memristor based architectures for storage and computation have been the object of a significant research effort, which has spawned a great number of publications and patents. Much of this interest is due to the memristor being a simple 2-terminal device as well as to its non-volatile nature. Last but not least, great interest is placed in the memristor's ability to perform both storage and processing operations on the same device^[6].

We describe here an experimental achievement which adds a conceptually new capability to state of the art memristors and show that a memristor operated by spin polarized electrodes

displays outstanding performances in information processing. With this Magnetically Enhanced Memristor (MEM) we succeeded in realizing an AND logic gate on the basis of *one single* device. We will also present evidence for the high potential and versatility of our devices by routinely achieving 32 distinct states, as a prerequisite for 5-bit memory operation. The memristance can have different origins in different materials. The first experimental report^[4] presented a device in which hysteretic current–voltage characteristics were ascribed to a particular interaction of electronic and ionic transport at the nanoscale, due to a reversible drift of the oxygen vacancies in the titanium oxide layer driven by the external voltage^[7]. Several more oxide materials have shown memristive properties since then, for example Gd_2O_3 ^[8], Ta_2O_5 ^[9].

Non-volatile resistance modifications have been also observed in a number of organic materials^[10], although the term memristor was used only in very few cases (see for example ref.^[11]). The introduction of organic materials into this field looks extremely attractive because of their potential for downscaling and because of the enormous choice of molecules, cheap fabrication and functionalization ability. Organic materials have recently made a spectacular progress in optoelectronics and electronics, with OLEDs (Organic LEDs) reaching performances compatible with the most appealing commercial applications^[12] and the realization of laboratory prototypes of high performance organic TFT^[13]. In this context the development of efficient organic memristors would produce valuable memory and processing units that could be built within the same technology.

We present in this paper the information processing capability of a memristor based on Alq₃ (Tris(8-hydroxyquinoline)aluminium(III)) and operated by spin polarized electrodes. Alq₃ is one of the most widely used organic semiconductors in OLEDs technology^[12, 14] as well as a major player in the field of organic spintronics^[15]. Devices based on these materials show a giant magnetoresistance (GMR) effect which is usually ascribed to injection and transport of spin polarized currents between the two electrodes^[16-18].

The GMR effect exists only at low voltage biases ($< 1\text{ V}$). At higher voltages (about 1-3 V) we detected a strong non-volatile electric resistive switching^[19], showing the typical memristor behaviour. It has been recently shown that magnetic and electric effects are interwoven and that a pre-applied programming voltage can reduce or even cancel the magnetoresistance output measured at low biases^[20].

In more detail, the devices presented in this paper consist of a 20 nm thick bottom $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ (LSMO) electrode, on which a layer of Alq_3 (with thickness ranging between 50 nm and 250 nm) is evaporated. The top electrode consists of a 20 nm thick Co film, separated from the Alq_3 by a 2 nm thick AlO_x tunnel barrier (Figure 1). The presence of the AlO_x provides at least two functions: it prevents the diffusion of top electrode species to the organic layer, and it considerably the magnetism of Co^[21-23]. All experimental data presented in the paper were collected at 100 K.

The four panels in Figure 2 elucidate the operation of the MEM. The I-V curves (Figure 2a) have two non-volatile branches that switch from high (low) to low (high) resistance states at threshold negative (positive) voltages. The two branches intersect at the origin, that is to say they form a “pinched hysteresis loop”, a clear memristor fingerprint^[24]. A negative differential resistance (NDR) part can be observed at high negative voltages, where the device switches to a higher resistance. Figure 2b shows that the memory capability provided by this combination of materials goes well beyond a simple two state behaviour. We observed a multitude of non-volatile resistance states that are controlled by the programming voltage. In other words it is possible to move within the NDR region and stop in a selected intermediate resistive state. The 32 resistive states in Figure 2b were obtained by applying a series of programming voltages starting from -1 V and adding -0.05 V voltage steps. The states differ, on average, by 20% from each other, offering promising possibilities for 5-bit memory applications. The positive voltage part behaves differently, with a less controllable switching toward the lowest resistance.

While Figure 2b demonstrates the remarkable “quantitative” performances as far as the standard memristor behaviour is concerned (to the best of our knowledge this is the finest resistance control so far reported for a memristor), the application of spin polarized electrodes brings into play significant qualitative modifications. Figure 2c shows strong magnetoresistance effects detected on various resistive states: the clearly visible dips correspond to electrodes being in the antiparallel orientation, while the non modulated resistance state reflects the parallel electrodes orientation. This inverse GMR effect is well accounted for the LSMO-Alq₃-Co systems, although its explanation (which is beyond the scope of this paper) was proposed only recently^[25]. The GMR effect is obviously measured at low voltage biases (-0.1V) which are small enough to preserve the memristance state. Moreover, the magnetoresistance is detected in such devices only for absolute voltage values that do not exceed ~0.5 V (red lines in Figure 2a). One can see that the GMR strength is smoothly reduced from about 20% to zero as one moves to higher resistance states. We assign the label ON to the state with the highest GMR, while the label OFF represents any of the states without GMR. On figure 2b the presence or absence of GMR are indicated by red and black colours respectively, while figure 2d shows the full set of both resistance and GMR values as a function of the programming voltage, with red colour symbols indicating non-zero GMR and corresponding memristance states.

The inset to Figure 2a shows the details of the NDR part in the negative voltage region. The curve measured with a high resolution (1 mV steps) displays an evident step like resistivity switching. Similar behaviour has been already reported for fully inorganic resistive switching devices and was associated to multiple conductive filaments^[26].

It is important to mention that we observed no clear dependence of the spanned memristance range on the thickness of the organic spacer in different devices (data to be published elsewhere). Similar uncorrelated behaviour with thickness is also characteristic for the GMR

strength in organic spin valves fabricated from the same materials^[27, 28]. We will come back to this issue in the discussion part.

Although a coarse GMR modification by moving from one memristance branch to another has been recently reported for the same system^[20] and for inorganic memristors with spin polarized electrodes^[29], the data presented above demonstrates a continuous control of the GMR magnitude going beyond a simple step-wise behaviour.

We move now to the second main goal of the paper – the demonstration of a working logic gate based on the MEM and its comparison with a standard memristor.

It has been recently demonstrated that memristors represent a very valuable solution for logic gates: the execution of the material implication (IMP), a universal Boolean logic operation, was performed with a system involving two memristors connected in parallel^[30]. We demonstrate now that the MEM has additional advantages over “standard” memristors, due to the fact that the magnetic field acts as a second input line added to the applied electric potential.

Figure 3 shows the experimental realization of another universal logic gate, AND, built with only a single MEM device. As the first input line of the logic gate we take the programming bias pulses needed to set the device in the low resistance state (ON state, value 1) or the high resistance state (OFF state, value 0). The magnetic field controls the second input line: the zero value (0) is assigned to the saturation field of 3 kOe (in principle 300-400 Oe are already sufficient for this, see Fig. 2c), corresponding to the electrodes magnetization in parallel orientation, while the value 1 is assigned to the field that leads to the antiparallel configuration.

The graph in Figure 3a shows the experimental output of the MEM depending on the different values of the inputs. After the application of the input signals, the -100 mV reading bias is set on the device and the experimentally measured current is reported. By setting a threshold in the output current (cyan line in the figure) it is possible to assign value 1 for currents

exceeding the threshold and 0 for lower currents. As shown in the truth table (Figure 3b) this coding leads to the realization of the “AND” logic gate with only one MEM device. For comparison, we note that by using standard memristors the “AND” gate is made of no less than 4 devices.

While the application of a magnetic field might look as an additional technological complication, it has to be considered that the magnetic field produced by one current line can serve a number of MEMs assembled in an array. Moreover the MEM could be integrated with domain-wall based magnetic memories (for example, race-track memory^[31] or magnet-based logics^[32]) where the magnetically stored information can act as a input B for our device.

In our devices it is possible to observe a good memristor behaviour up to room temperature, while, on the other hand, the utilization of LSMO as a spin polarized electrode limits the room temperature GMR to values below 1%, preventing its operation as a logic gate. We believe that further materials research will provide sufficient GMR strength at room temperature, bringing these devices closer to real applications.

The clear correlation between the two curves in Figure 2c, not only provides hints for the understanding of memristive mechanisms, it suggests that established resistive memory models represent an additional key for the analysis of spintronic effects in such or similar devices. We speculate that the new data discussed in this paper together with data published in a number of reports^[19, 20, 27, 28] can be explained on the basis of filamentary conductivity as essential mechanism underlying both resistive switching in investigated stacks and spin transport in Alq₃. Indeed filaments were widely used for the description of numerous non-spintronic devices and materials featuring non-volatile resistive switching [Citation]. While in some devices the filaments were deliberately created by the migration of the top electrode species [Cit TEM], generally the filaments need not be necessarily aggregates of diffused top electrode material [der Holst]^[33-35]. While in some devices the filaments were on purpose created by the migration of the top electrode species^[36], generally the filaments need not be

necessarily aggregates of diffused top electrode material^[37, 38] (see above the discussion on the AlO_x role).

The first piece of evidence comes from a long standing issue in organic spintronics, typical of this device geometry and this materials combination: in spite of the fact that LUMO and HOMO levels of Alq₃ are separated by injection barriers of about 1 eV^[23, 39] the GMR in such devices is measured at voltages as low as 1 mV and actually not exceeding 0.5-1 V^[17, 18]. This clearly requires the presence of conducting channels able to build at least one continuous path connecting the two electrodes and whose energy levels fall within the gap of Alq₃.

The presence of filaments can also explain the random thickness dependence of both GMR and resistive switching effects mentioned above and previously discussed for pure spintronic effects in LSMO/Alq₃/Co based devices^[27, 28]. Indeed both the length distribution and the number of conducting filaments would have a rather complex and non-trivial dependence on the thickness, resulting in an apparent random thickness dependence for the investigated range. We claim, on the other hand, that explanations based on tunnelling across 10-100 nm of Alq₃ as well as possible purely interface phenomena (for example, very high and strongly scattered interface resistance), are in contradiction with the first piece of evidence, namely low voltage transport.

Last but not least, filaments provide a simple explanation of the multistate behaviour shown in Figure 2b (32 memristive states), via progressive blocking of filaments connected in parallel. In addition, as mentioned above, the step-wise shape of the NDR region shown in the inset to Figure 2a was already identified as a sign of filamentary conductivity^[26].

The filamentary conduction framework offers also clear and physically meaningful mechanisms that can account for the GMR variation with programming voltage. The GMR reduction in this context would be due to either different spin depolarization in filaments of different quality or geometry (for example higher depolarization in longer filaments), or to a decrease in charge injection and possibly in spin injection at the interface. Here the

connection between the electrode and the filament is modified or interrupted upon the application of the programming voltage. **An important but yet unclear to us fact is that while the electric switching repeatability persists up to 10^4 cycles, the GMR effect endurance is much shorter disappearing within some tens of cycles.**

While the involvement of the filaments to explain both charge and spin transport in Alq_3 -based GMR devices is a significant step ahead, a complete model for spin and charge transport in Alq_3 and related interfaces requires a clear identification of material species involved in filaments formation and their on-off switching mechanisms. In this context the intersection between the two switching effects offers valuable constraints for a better understanding of both of them.

In summary, we demonstrated that memristors operated by spin polarized electrodes (MEMs) can operate as a complete logic gate built on one single device. A direct proof of concept was demonstrated via the experimental realization of the “AND” logic gate. MEMs are fully compatible with the simple cross-bar geometry, typical of 2-terminal devices, and exploit all of its technological advantages. At the same time, the device properties are considerably enriched by using the magnetic field as a non-contact third terminal. The ability of MEM to feature a large (nearly continuous) number of magnetically modulated memristances allows us to vary the logic gate threshold value in a wide interval making the device adaptable towards integration into logic circuits. Moreover, promising high memory capability (32 states and hence 5-bit storage) promotes the utilization of MEM in memory applications.

The development of the MEM follows the strategy of integrating different functionalities on the same device rather than increasing the density of the fundamental components of integrated circuits.

The realization of this device is a clear example of how novel material properties promote new device paradigms. Finally, this work suggests that targeted modifications of the memristor can lead to significant progress on a wide range of ICT applications.

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Figure 1 . Schematic layout of our device. From the top: Co ferromagnetic electrode, followed by a thin AlO_x tunnel barrier, a layer of the organic semiconductor Alq₃ and finally the bottom La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}MnO₃ ferromagnetic electrode. The final device area is 1 mm². The input bias voltage is applied to INPUT A and the corresponding current is measured by the ammeter A. The resistance of the device is defined as $R = V_R/A$. The GMR is obtained by measuring R as a function of the applied magnetic field (INPUT A). When the magnetizations of the two ferromagnetic electrodes are oriented antiparallel to each other the device resistance is lower than the parallel case.

Figure 2 Measures showed here are taken on a sample with 200 nm thick Alq₃ layer, at 100K. a) Typical memristor pinched I-V curve. Inset: high resolution I-V of the NDR region. b) sequence of I-V curves reaching increasingly higher (50mV step) negative biases (programming bias). The red curves correspond to programming biases that leave the device with GMR signal. The black curves reach programming biases high enough to destroy the GMR signal. c) GMR curves taken at -100mV in the ON state (red points), intermediate state (red circles) and OFF state (black points). d) here the resistance state at -100mV shown in circles and the GMR magnitude are shown as a function of the applied programming bias (with I-V curves from panel c)). Red and black colours correspond to the presence or otherwise of the GMR as in the other panels.

	A (Program. Bias)	B (Magnetic Field)	Out (AND)
OFF	0	⇒ 0	0
OFF	0	⇐ 1	0
ON	1	⇒ 0	0
ON	1	⇐ 1	1

Figure 3. a) Inputs and detected output of SEM used as a logic “AND” gate. Input A corresponds to programming bias pulses needed to set the device in the low resistance state (ON state, value 1) or the high resistance state (OFF state, value 0). Input B is represented by the magnetic field: the zero value bit (0) corresponds to the parallel orientation of the electrodes magnetization (in this case 3 kOe), while the value 1 is assigned to the antiparallel configuration. After the application of the input signals the device is read at -100mV and the measured current that represents the logic gate output is reported in graph a). These are experimentally collected data, taken after the application of the proper input signals. By setting a threshold in the output current (cyan line in the graph) it is possible to assign 1 for currents more negative than the threshold and 0 for lower currents. A single cycle, represented by the four combinations of inputs, is showed in the Inset. The “AND” logic gate truth table (panel b) is reproduced by using only one single device.

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Memristors, together with spintronic devices, are among the most promising candidates for future ICT architectures. For the first time, we present two experimental proof of concepts of possible applications spawn by the intermixing of spintronic and memristive effects into a single device we called Magnetically Enhanced Memristor (MEM). We obtained 32 different resistance states (which also show different GMR amplitude) setting the MEM as a good candidate for a 5-bit memory. Finally, by exploiting the interaction between the memristance and the GMR signal, we experimentally realize an AND logic gate based on a *single* MEM device.

Keyword (see list)

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Single device logic gate and multi-bit memory based on Magnetically Enhanced Memristor

ToC figure ((55 mm broad, 50 mm high, or 110 mm broad, 20 mm high))